

**LET'S HAVE AN EXPERIENCE REQUIREMENT FOR
ACCOUNTING EDUCATORS: AN ECONOMIC & ETHICAL
ANALYSIS**

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Abstract

The usual surrogates used to measure the quality of college professors are possession of a terminal degree or publications. This article advocates using relevant experience as a substitute for these surrogates.

There is no disagreement that we need good accounting educators. The accounting profession and the various accreditation agencies would agree on this point. The problem is that quality is difficult to measure, so surrogate methods have to be found to approximate the measurement of quality.

A few surrogates have been found and used over the years. There is the perception that someone who has a PhD is somehow more qualified to teach accounting than someone who does not have a PhD. Presumably, someone who has a professional certification such as the CMA, CPA or CIA is also more qualified to teach. There is also a presumption that someone who publishes on a regular basis is a better educator than someone who does not publish. It might also be argued that someone who takes classes or attends seminars is better qualified to teach than someone who

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does not. Student evaluation scores might also be used to evaluate the quality of accounting professors.

All of these surrogate measures of quality have their strong points and weak points. Someone who has completed a PhD program has passed through a number of gauntlets. Thus, some level of achievement has been attained. But there are problems with using the PhD as a surrogate of quality. For one thing, PhD programs require students to take much more than just accounting courses. In fact, some accounting PhD programs require only a few accounting courses. The majority of coursework at some prestigious universities don't include many accounting courses at all.

Another problem inherent in using the PhD as a surrogate for quality is the time element. Who is better qualified to teach, someone who earned the PhD 40 years ago or someone who earned a masters degree in accounting six months ago? Neither accreditation agencies nor colleges and universities take this factor into account when evaluating the quality of accounting educators.

A similar argument could be made for those holding certification. Who is better qualified to teach, someone who passed the CPA exam 40 years ago or someone who recently completed a masters degree in accounting? Of course, most certification agencies now require continuing education in order to maintain certification, which minimizes the possibility of becoming out of date. But many continuing education programs leave much to be desired. The vast majority of such programs do not test participants, for example. Also, some programs are of quite poor quality. I once received CPE credit for listening to Art Buchwald tell accounting jokes, for example. The jokes were quite good but I don't think I learned anything that I could apply to a professional engagement.

Publication is one way to determine whether an educator is current in the field. Presumably, someone who has been able to find a journal willing to publish his or her article has something to add to the literature of the discipline. Accounting practitioners who have ever read some of the more esoteric accounting journals

would dispute this claim, however. In fact, the publish or perish syndrome that has permeated the universities can be unhealthy and can adversely affect the quality of accounting education. If educators must publish a certain number of articles to maintain their position at the university, they have less time to spend on class preparation and other activities that could enhance their classroom performance.

One surrogate of quality that has been virtually ignored – or even castigated – is relevant, recent and practical experience. Accreditation agencies do not require accounting educators to have any accounting experience at all. It is quite possible to become a tenured full professor without having ever worked in either public or private accounting. Educators receive no credit for having accounting experience. Deans, department chairs and rank & tenure committees look at publications and PhDs but not experience. In fact, accounting educators at some schools are encouraged to downplay any experience they might have, lest they be viewed negatively by some members of the rank & tenure committee. It has been my experience that committee members from Arts & Sciences, who often tend to hold business school applicants in low regard anyway because they earn more than Arts & Sciences professors, will use practical experience as an excuse to vote to deny promotion or tenure. One member of my own business school rank & tenure committee voted to deny me tenure because of the perception that I made a pile of money from outside consulting. I got tenure anyway and, for the record, I did not (at that time, at least) make a pile of money from outside consulting. But that is not the point. The point is that accounting educators are being penalized for maintaining their skills through outside consulting. They are even viewed negatively by some powerful segments of academia for ever having worked in their profession. If the quality of accounting education is to be improved, that attitude must change, or at least the damage that can be done by those who hold such attitudes must be minimized.

Here is what I propose. Agencies that accredit accounting programs should add an experience requirement.² Arguably, someone who has accounting experience is a better classroom teacher than someone who has not had any accounting experience. There are exceptions, of course, but most people who have been taught both by professors who have had accounting experience and by those who have not would generally agree that those who have accounting experience tend to be better classroom teachers than those who have not.

My own experience in this regard is not untypical. When I took the masters degree program in taxation at DePaul University back in the 1970s, most of my professors were part-timers who worked as partners at Arthur Young during the day. They came in one night a week and taught their specialty, the same subject that they were working at during the day. They were all either good or excellent. The one full-time PhD I had was mediocre, at best. When students asked him a practice type question he was usually not able to answer. The part-timers, on the other hand, could give real life examples to illustrate their point.

A mandatory experience requirement could take several forms. I do not think that adding an experience requirement to the

² This proposal assumes acceptance of the premise that accreditation agencies should exist in the first place. That premise needs to be examined in light of the fact that the "private" accreditation agencies we think of, such as the North Central Association and the American Assembly of Collegiate Schools of Business, are granted monopoly status by the Department of Education in Washington, DC. So how private can they be? They certainly do not have to respond to market forces, since they have no legal competition. As is the case with any monopoly, price is higher and quality is lower than would be the case under a market system, where competition is not snuffed out by government. However, an examination of this issue would take us too far afield from the main point of the article, so we will defer discussion of this issue for another day. Suffice it to say that, in a market system, if having teachers who were experienced in the subject they taught had any value, that value would be reflected. In the present accreditation system it is not only not reflected positively but is reflected negatively, in the sense that teachers who have actually practiced what they teach have one or two strikes against them when they apply for promotion or tenure.

existing requirements – PhD and publications – would benefit accounting education. If those holding PhDs were required to also have experience, many of them would have to be fired (which might not be a bad idea, but that is another issue). I suggest that an experience requirement be made an alternative way to evaluate quality. At present, a professor who holds a PhD is considered terminally qualified regardless of experience. I suggest that, in lieu of a PhD, someone who has let's say five years accounting experience, or three years experience plus some kind of relevant masters degree or certification, be terminally qualified to teach undergraduates. To teach at the masters level, a bit more experience would be required, perhaps seven years, or five years plus a masters or certification. To teach PhD students, ten years experience would be required. Teaching experience should not count toward meeting the experience requirement. Experience should be in public, private or nonprofit accounting.

If experience were made mandatory, it would help to alleviate the present bias that exists against those who have experience. It would also encourage those who might not otherwise have experience to get some experience. Students would also benefit, since they would be taught by individuals who learned by doing rather than by reading.

The experience requirement should also include some current component. Being taught by someone who got his five or ten years experience thirty years ago does little to ensure quality. There should be some requirement that accounting educators have a certain amount of recent experience. Perhaps 500 hours a year working in some accounting capacity would be sufficient. Or perhaps 1,500 hours over a three-year period could be set as a minimum.

Some academics would argue that having a 500-hour a year requirement would not be possible because of the need to publish, which is time-consuming. However, the experience requirement should be classified as an alternative to publication, not an additional requirement. Those who meet the current experience requirement would not be required to publish, although they should

be free to do so if they choose. Five hundred hours is not much at all. It's only about one day a week. And it's all anyone really needs to keep current in some subfield of accounting. Five hundred hours a year would also be sufficient to provide current examples in the classroom.

Having an experience requirement along the lines I have outlined would go a long way toward improving accounting education. It would greatly enhance the possibility that accounting students would be exposed to educators who actually gained some experience by doing the things they are teaching.

How do we get from here to there? The possibility that the academic segment of the accounting profession would pick up the ball and run with it is remote, at best. Academics have a vested interest in keeping things as they are. Any pressure for change must come from outside the academic community. At the very least, the groups that represent accountants, like the AICPA, IMA, IIA and various state accounting groups should make their voices heard. The large accounting firms and corporations, many of which recruit on campuses and provide funding for accounting programs, should also let it be known that they are dissatisfied with the present situation. If a few major monetary contributors to accounting education threaten to reduce or cut off funding, the academic segment of the profession will start to pay attention. Until the academics feel pressure from the outside, they will not reform the present system.